
Understanding the Impact of COVID-19 on Agriculture and Food Supply Chains:

System Dynamics Modeling for the Resilience of Smallholder Farmers

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The COVID-19 pandemic has led to severe disruptions in the supply and demand channels of agriculture and food chains. As a fundamental approach to addressing complex social, managerial, economic, or ecological problems, system dynamics models have been used to provide a shared understanding of agriculture and food systems resilience and to enhance decision-making for policy actions. To begin to address challenges arising from this pandemic, eight system dynamics researchers from different countries participated (virtually) in a group model building study. The project, “Agriculture and Food Supply Chain Resilience in the Face of a Health Crisis”, emerged as an initiative of the Agriculture Food Special Interest Group of the System Dynamics Society. As a result of the project, a stock-flow diagram with nine modules (Food Supply Chain, Food Market, Farm Finance, Agricultural Inputs, Labor, Shelf Life, Cooperation, Information, and Community Health) was built to understand the effects of the pandemic from the viewpoint of small-scale farmer communities. This preprint has been prepared and distributed to facilitate dialogue and to generate feedback from researchers interested in providing modeling solutions to mitigate the effects of these disruptions and enhancing agriculture and food supply chain resilience.

*For more information about the project, please request the full text of the preprint via ResearchGate, **Agriculture and Food Supply Chain Resilience in the Face of a Health Crisis** or contact authors via e-mail: ¹busra.atamer@metu.edu.tr, ⁴kelechiodoemen@gmail.com, ⁵bob@foundationforinclusion.org, ⁸arpitha@foundationforinclusion.org.*